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ABSTRACTS

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Effect of Fly ash & Microbes on Strength properties of Subgrade soil for Pavements

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Abstract: This work investigates the utilization of microbial-induced calcite precipitation (MICP) treatment to improve the stability of soil by introducing Class F fly ash and *Bacillus subtilis* microbes. Various experiments were carried out using soil that was readily available in the vicinity area. The primary tasks consisted of mixing fly ash and subsequently utilizing varying quantities of fly-ash. The experiment involved the incorporation of fly ash at varying ratios, specifically 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. The soil's characteristics are influenced by the presence of fly ash, as evidenced by the following tests: reduction in liquid limit, increase in UCC and CBR values, analysis of soil compaction under high pressure, measurement of unconfined compressive strength (UCC) at various time intervals (0, 3, 7, 14, and 21 days), and assessment of California bearing ratio (CBR) for soil samples with varying amounts of fly ash. The most favorable results are obtained by integrating 25% fly ash into the soil, surpassing all other quantities. Following the introduction of *Bacillus subtilis* C4nc8 bacteria, the OMC is blended with a mixture consisting of 25% fly ash and soil. In addition, it is shown that the optimal values for CBR (2.2 times higher than that of soil) and UCC (6.5 times higher than that of pure soil) are attained by blending soil with 25% fly ash and microorganisms. Ultimately, the addition of soil, 25% fly ash, and microorganisms has been discovered to significantly improve the CBR strength of the subgrade.

Keywords: Fly ash, clayey sand, microbes, ucc, cbr.

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